

Experimental Report P5936, MID September 18-19 2023
Coherent X-ray Speckle Correlation Imaging

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We were given 2 days as in house to study the implementation of Ptychography and Coherent X-ray Speckle Correlation Imaging (CSCI) at MID in the hard x-ray regime. This novel technique is capable of reconstructing the single shot wave fields of X-ray pulses with tens of nm resolution enabling the single-shot imaging and beam characterization. The core principle of the CSCI is to use the highly-scattering object (diffuser) with the known and highly-randomized transfer function (TF) to scatter the wave field of interest. First, due to the high randomness of TF, this produces speckle diffraction pattern complex enough for the single-shot phase retrieval [1]. Additionally, the produced diffraction patterns have lower dynamical range thus allowing to have more photons on the detector before saturation.

We had the following experimental plan: First, perform ptychographic reconstruction of the known resolution target sample to perform preliminary characterization of the X-ray beam at MID; Then do the ptychographic measurements of the diffuser to check if the simulated transfer function is close to the real one at 9keV; finally, to measure the separate set of diffraction patterns with diffuser in, to test the single-shot reconstruction capabilities of CSCI. In total we spend 24 hours performing these measurements.

Figure 1 Sketch of the experimental setup at MID at 9 keV. The beam was focused using 50 Be CRLs to 100 nm. The sample was located 10 mm after the focal plane, the diffuser used in CSCI 10 mm downstream the sample. The sample-detector distance was 9555 mm.

Figure 1 shows the experimental setup used at MID. The X-ray beam had a photon energy of 9keV. We used a pink beam with 30 eV (SASE) bandwidth with 10Hz repetition rate. The 50 Be compound refractive lenses focused the incoming x-rays to 100 nm with a focal length of 300 mm. The Siemens star (Au on Si) resolution target was located 10 mm downstream the

focus on a piezo stage (PI). The diffuser (W with through holes on Si used in [1]) was located 10 mm downstream the sample in a second set of piezo motors (SmarAct). The detector (Jungfrau) was located 9.55 m from the Diffuser.

Figure 2. Ptychographically reconstructed phase of the test sample. Pixel size is 40 nm.

First, we ptychographic reconstruction of the known test sample. The scanning of the sample was performed using the PI stage. The beam had a size of roughly 5 μm at the sample plane. A mesh scan consisted from 10x10 steps with the step size of 1 μm . In this part of the experiment the diffuser was out of the beam trajectory. The ptychographic reconstruction was performed using the automatic-differentiation based engine described in [2] (this and all further reconstructions were performed on the A100 GPU at Maxwell cluster and took 5 minutes for Ptychography and 10 seconds for CSCI). Figure 2 (right) shows the phase of the reconstructed test sample TF. The main mode of the reconstructed X-ray beam is shown in Figure 4. (e).

During the next part of the experiment, we performed the ptychographic reconstruction of the diffuser TF. In this case the Siemens star was kept outside of the beam trajectory, diffuser was inserted in the beam and the beam size at the diffuser was set to roughly 5 μm . The reconstruction of the diffuser was performed in the same manner as Siemens Star using the previously reconstructed beam modes as the starting probe guess to improve the

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convergence for the small features on diffuser. The reconstructed phase of the diffuser TF is shown in the right side of Figure 3. The reconstructed Diffuser TF was compared with the designed TF (left side of Figure 3.) and found to be close.

After that we measured the separate series of the diffraction patterns with diffuser in the beam.

Measured diffraction patterns were treated by the CSCI reconstruction algorithm similar to the one described in [1].

Figure 3. Designed (left) and ptychographically reconstructed (right) phase of the diffuser. Pixel size is 40 nm.

Figure 5. Reconstructed wave fields at the diffuser plane. (a-d) Single-shot reconstructions produced from four individual X-ray pulses. (e) Main mode reconstructed by ptychography from the scanning dataset of 121 scan positions.. Complex values are represented using domain coloring, hue represents phase and saturation represents amplitude.

Figure 4. Reconstructed wave fields from Figure 4, propagated to the focal plane. Complex values are represented using domain coloring, hue represents phase and saturation represents amplitude. Yellow lines are shown to highlight shot-to-shot fluctuations.

The reconstructed wave fields at the diffuser plane are shown in Figure 4 (a-d). The wave fields are close to the obtained by the ptychographic reconstruction and demonstrate the similar resolution (40 nm). Both techniques provide the complex wave fields making it possible to study the aberrations of the optical system and examination of the focal plane by back-propagation (Shown at Figure 5.) However, contrary to the averaged modes and shot-to-shot varying modal weights reconstructed by ptychography, CSCI reconstructions are obtained from the individual diffraction patterns and thus can directly show shot-to-shot fluctuations of the X-ray beam. Additionally, being the single pulse technique CSCI has a huge potential for the pump-probe applications. The shot-to-shot fluctuations are visible in the reconstructions as global shifts of the wavefields (beam pointing variation), change in the intensity distribution could be related to the input aperture of the CRLs stack or from the different coherent modes generated by XFEL accelerator.

Considering these results, demonstration the potential of CSCI for single-shot imaging and beam characterization at MID. we would like to apply for beamtime to retrieve single shots wave fields using a higher repetition rate. We think that the Ultrafast dynamical diffraction studies [3] present a perfect match to our project, since they would greatly benefit from both single-shot capacities CSCI and its ability to provide high-resolution complex valued reconstructions of wave fields.

References:

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